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STAR4BBS final conference Report

UnitelmaSapienza
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STAR4BBS final conference Report

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Partners short names

TUB	(Technische Universität Berlin)
UNITELMA	(Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma)
UNI	(Ente Italiano di Normazione)
AUA	(Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon)
USC	(Universidad de Santiago de Compostela)
APRE	(Agenzia per la promozione della Ricerca Europea)
NOVA	(Nova - Institut für politische und Ökologische Innovation GMBH)
BAM	(Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und Prüfung)
RSB	(Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association)
ISEAL	(ISEAL Alliance)

Abbreviations

BMS	BIOBASED Monitoring System
BMT	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool
CSLs	Certification Schemes and Labels
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
DPP	Digital Product Passport
DoA	Description of Action
ECD	Empowering Consumers Directive
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
PP	Privacy Policy
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
SCS	Sustainability Certification Schemes
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This report provides an overview of the **BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Conference**, jointly organized by the STAR4BBS, the HARMONITOR and the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED projects.

The event marked a key milestone in the dissemination of project results and facilitated in-depth stakeholder engagement on the future of voluntary sustainability certification in the bio-based sector, along with the launch and future exploitation of the BMT using the web tool.

Held in Brussels in May 2025, the conference brought together over 80 participants from academia, industry, certification bodies, policy institutions, and civil society. The event showcased the **BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT)** as a potential co-regulatory policy instrument, explored the evolving role of sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs), and examined their feasibility, impacts, and alignment with EU legislation such as the **Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)** and the **Empowering Consumers Directive (ECD)**.

The conference featured panel discussions, interactive workshops, and a collaborative closing session to develop joint policy recommendations. Participants reflected on certification schemes' potential to support a sustainable, circular bioeconomy and identified practical strategies to enhance the credibility, uptake, and coherence of SCS across Europe.

This deliverable summarises the organisational approach, participation, key discussion points, and strategic outputs generated during the conference. It provides insights into stakeholder needs, priorities, and expectations, contributing to the broader policy dialogue on sustainability governance in the EU bioeconomy.

1 Introduction

STAR4BBS (Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems) is a Horizon Europe-funded project launched in September 2022. It aims to maximize the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels in facilitating a successful transition toward a sustainable bio-based economy. This multidisciplinary and multi-actor initiative focuses on developing a fit-for-purpose monitoring system to assess the effectiveness, robustness, and traceability of existing international and EU-level certification schemes and labels related to biological feedstocks, bio-based materials, and products.

The project involved important stakeholders¹ (scheme owners, policy makers, and industry) in the design of the research and the monitoring system and in the development of practical recommendations emerging from the research and analysis, in order to ensure that the project achieves its goal.

The final conference of the STAR4BBS project was envisaged (as set out in the DoA, Task 7.5) as an onsite conference in order to raise awareness amongst target groups about the results of the project and encouraging their uptake (e.g. tools created, recommendations co-created with stakeholders, etc.). It was conceived as a moment to gather decision makers, stakeholders and other relevant actors, as well as journalists of relevant media, at European, regional and international level.

Thanks to the great collaborations established with sister projects in the BIOBASEDCERT cluster, it was decided—also in agreement with the European Commission’s policy and project officers—that joining forces with the other projects funded under the same call would maximize impact, avoid duplication of efforts, and ensure greater visibility of the cluster’s collective results. This collaborative approach was fully aligned with the DoA’s intention of holding the STAR4BBS final conference close to other relevant sector events and in synergy with sister projects, thereby strengthening outreach to decision makers, stakeholders, and the wider bioeconomy community.

For this reason, the STAR4BBS project final conference was converted into the BIOBASEDCERT Final Conference.

2 Final conference overview and goal

The BIOBASEDCERT Final Conference aimed to present key outcomes from the BIOBASEDCERT cluster and position them within the broader context of EU bioeconomy policies. The event fostered dialogue and co-creation among stakeholders to explore how **voluntary sustainability certification schemes** can support a **sustainable circular bioeconomy**.

Through interactive sessions, workshops, and panel discussions, the conference sought to:

- Demonstrate the potential of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) as a co-regulatory policy instrument;
- Analyse the role of certification schemes and labels in enhancing transparency, trust, and sustainability across bio-based value chains;
- Explore the implications of EU policy developments (e.g., Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation¹ and Directive Empowering Consumers for the Green Transition²) for bio-based products;
- Evaluate the feasibility, costs, and benefits of voluntary sustainability certification systems;
- Develop joint policy recommendations and identify actionable steps to align certification with EU green transition goals.

The event ultimately aimed to generate strategic insights and foster alignment between research results, certification practices, and evolving EU sustainability policies.

The conference was organised as a full-day event, featuring presentations, several expert panels from diverse fields, and an **interactive Mentimeter exercise** that kept the audience engaged and encouraged real-time feedback.

During the **lunch break**, a game developed by a related project was showcased, sparking great interest and offering an engaging way to explore sustainability themes. The day concluded with a **networking cocktail**, which facilitated informal exchanges among participants and allowed deeper discussions on key topics addressed during the day.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for sustainable products, amending Directive (EU) 2020/1828 and Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 and repealing Directive 2009/125/EC. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R1781&qid=1719580391746>

² Directive (EU) 2024/825 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 February 2024 amending Directives 2005/29/EC and 2011/83/EU as regards empowering consumers for the green transition through better protection against unfair practices and through better information. Available at:

3 BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Conference organization

The event was jointly organised by the three sister projects (STAR4BBS, HARMONITOR and SUSTCERT4BIO), with STAR4BBS coordinating and overseeing the overall organization, and with the support of the Project Officer at the EC venue.

For the organization of BIOBASEDCERT final conference, we followed the consistent methodology already validated for the co-creation events (D6.2)³. APRE was responsible for the overall organization, and logistics, supported by TUB for the scientific contents, as well as sister projects and technical partners.

3.1 Agenda

During the preparation phase, the coordinators of the three projects of the BIOBASEDCERT cluster held meetings on a regular basis and identified the core activities, the programme and the sessions format and length, as well as the main speakers in the panels. The organising team divided the agenda into 4 sessions; for each session, a facilitator was selected to chair it, present the panellists and propose the set of questions previously defined.

The organising team developed the detailed programme, including information on the scope, purpose, structure and activities of the event, clearly explaining participants' expected roles and contributions.

The agenda included the following elements:

- A welcome and introduction section to open the event effectively, and to clearly present the goals, agenda, and workshop etiquette.
- Sufficient time after each session for participants to network and interact, helping them fully engage with the workshop's main subject;
- Breaks and energizers for participants both in presence and online events, to maintain concentration and support team building;
- Time for closing, reflection and feedback. Participants were invited to share their considerations and questions on the topics discussed. In some cases, questionnaires were sent afterwards to gather inputs for future collaborations or for other workshops.

The draft agenda was sent in advance with the invitation link, and shared on the projects' websites.

³ Available in Zenodo and in the project database <https://star4bbs.eu/public-results/>

The final agenda is shown below in Table 1:

Table 1: BIOBASEDCERT final event agenda

09:00-12:30- Morning session	
9:00- 9:15 Opening	<p>Opening Agenda and Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Luana Ladu (TU Berlin) <p>Welcome and introduction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unit Green Transitions, DG Research & Innovation at European Commission - Astrid Ladefoged Stefania Rocca (Project Officer, European Research Executive Agency, REA)
9:15 – 10:45- Session I “Exploring the applicability of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) as a co-regulation instrument”	
<p><u>Moderator:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Iris Vural Gursel (Wageningen Research) 	<p>9:15 – 10:00 BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool - BMT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> BMT: Introduction and applicability (Luana Ladu, TUB) System Level (Nikola Matović, TUB) Content Level (Heleen Ballemans, WR) Outcome Level (Maulidia Khairani, UU) <p>10:00 – 10:10 Q&A from all participants</p> <p>10:10 – 10:40 Panel discussion with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jiannis Kougoulis (DG GROW) Blanca de Ulibarri (RSB) Audrun Utskarpen (Nordic Swan) Martin Junginger (3-CO + BIOBASEDCERT Cluster) Rodrigo Rupérez (UNCTAD) <p>10:40 – 10:45 Summary – recommendations</p>
10:45– 11:00	Coffee break
11:00- 12:30- Workshop: “Bio-based products and certification in the frame of the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and the Consumer Empowerment Directive”	
<p><u>Moderator:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Silvia Maltagliati (DG RTD at European Commission) 	<p>Panel discussion with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lara Dammer (nova-Institut) Luca Boniolo (ECOS) Maira Devisscher (ISEAL) René Bethmann (VAUDE) Ivana Krkljus (BASF) Floris Akkerman (BAM)
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch
13:30 – 17:30- Afternoon session	
13:30 - 14:30- Session II: “Impact of certification on global bio-based value chains”	

<p><u>Moderator:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lara Dammer (nova-Institut) 	<p>13:30 – 13:45 Presentations from the cluster (key results & recommendations)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Myrna van Leeuwen (WR) • Gabriela Lopez Camey (Preferred by Nature) • Luciano Proto Cassina (nova-Institut) <p>13:45 – 14:10 Interactive session</p> <p>14:10 – 14:25 Discussion of the project results, interactive session and conclusion</p> <p>14:25 – 14:30 Key takeaways</p>
<p>14:30 – 15:30- Session III: “Assessing the feasibility of voluntary sustainability certification: costs, benefits, challenges and ways forward”</p>	
<p><u>Moderator:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Birka Wicke (Radboud University) 	<p>14:30 – 14:50 Presentations from the cluster (key results & recommendations)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costanza Rossi (SQ-Consult) • Lusine Aramyan (WR) • Sofia Maria Ioannidou (AUA) <p>14:50 – 15:15 Panel discussion with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yuki Hamilton Onda Kabe (Braskem) • Laura Väyrynen (ECOS) • Harmen Willemse (Better Biomass) • Joyce de Wit (RVO) <p>15:15 – 15:25 Q&A from all participants</p> <p>15:25 – 15:30 Key takeaways</p>
<p>15:30 – 16:00</p>	<p><i>Coffee Break</i></p>
<p>16:00 – 17:20- Session IV: “How can voluntary sustainability certification schemes drive the transition to a sustainable bioeconomy”</p>	
<p><u>Moderators:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sergio Ugarte (SQ Consult) • Stefan Majer (DBFZ) 	<p>16:00 – 16:05 Welcome</p> <p>16:05 – 16:15 Projects4Future Workshop Insights: Tools and Recommendations on Standards, Certifications, Labelling and Monitoring for the Bioeconomy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Susanna Albertini (FVA New media Research) <p>16:15 – 16:30 Introduction and summary of key messages from previous sessions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iris Vural Gursel (Wageningen Research) • Silvia Maltagliati (DG RTD) • Birka Wicke (Radboud University) • Lara Dammer (nova-Institut) <p>16:30 – 16:45 Policy and platform recommendations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stefan Majer (DBFZ) <p>16:40 – 17:05 Discussion on recommendations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Piergiuseppe Morone (Unitelma la Sapienza) <p>17:05 – 17:20 Q&A with all participants and key take aways</p>

17:20 – 17:30	Closing remarks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Luana Ladu (TU Berlin)
17:30 – 19:00	Networking event

3.2 Invitations

This section includes detailed documentation to support the organisation of future conferences, covering invitation texts and the registration format used.

An initial “save the date” was sent to the consortia partners in October 2024.

The first invitation was sent to external stakeholders in February 2025, including information on the event (date, location, purpose and reason for the invitation) (Table 2) and the registration link with the consent form, following the GDPR rules applicable.

With the intention to reach a larger audience, we requested the consortium to disseminate the invitation email through their network. The Joint Advisory Board received a dedicated mail (see section. 3.2.1).

The text of the mail sent to all stakeholders is reported in the box below (Table 2):

Table 2: the text of the mail sent for invitation

<p>Dear All</p> <p>I hope this message finds you well.</p> <p>We are delighted to invite you to the Final Conference of the Horizon Europe projects STAR4BBS, HARMONITOR, and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, which have joined forces as the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster to implement joint activities supporting sustainability certification.</p> <p>This event will present the results of our projects, including the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), which is designed to evaluate the robustness, comprehensiveness and effectiveness of sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs). Additionally, we will present our Policy Recommendations, engaging key stakeholders. The workshop will bring together EU policymakers, CSLs owners, and other key stakeholders to discuss the evolving policy landscape shaping the transition towards sustainable bio-based systems.</p> <p>The conference will be held in Brussels on May 13th, 2025, at the CDMA European Commission - DG Research & Innovation (Marsveldstraat 21 Rue du Champ de Mars, 1050 Ixelles, Brussels).</p> <p><u>Please note that we must provide the European Commission with the list of names of the subscribers at least 15 days in advance to be able to access the</u></p>

building; those who are not in the list (via registration form) can not attend the meeting

We kindly ask all of you to confirm your participation by April 24th, 2025, by using:

For more details, please refer to the attached file and check <https://star4bbs.eu/biobasedcert-cluster-final-conference/>

If you have any questions, please feel free to contact us at star4bbs@apre.it

If you have already received this message and are either already registered or not interested, please disregard it, and we apologize for the inconvenience.

Best regards,
the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster organization team

A final reminder was sent to registered participants one week before the event, including the full invitation (detailed programme and information pack).

The list of confirmed people was sent to the EC to gain the access to the venue.

3.2.1 Invitations of Joint Advisory Board

As mentioned above, the Joint Advisory Board received a dedicated invitation (Table 3).

Table 3: the text of the mail sent to the Joint Advisory Board

Dear Joint Advisory Board Member,

We are delighted to invite you to the **Final Conference** organized by the Horizon Europe projects STAR4BBS, HARMONITOR, and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

The conference will be held in **Brussels on May 13th, 2025**, at the **CDMA European Commission - DG Research & Innovation**, Marsveldstraat 21 Rue du Champ de Mars, 1050 Ixelles.

This event will serve as an opportunity to present the final results of our projects. Notably, we will showcase the **BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT)**, which is designed to evaluate the robustness, comprehensiveness and effectiveness of sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs). Additionally, we will deliver our Policy Recommendations to our targeted stakeholders, including EU policy makers, and CSL owners.

Please note that the STAR4BBS project will cover the cost of your participation (respecting specific criteria).

Further details, including the program and logistical information, will be provided by the end of February. In the meantime, **we kindly request that you confirm your availability by emailing us at star4bbs@apre.it**, so we can send you a 'SAVE-THE-DATE' by the middle of January 2025.

We look forward to welcoming you at the Final Conference.

Best regards,

the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster organization team

Two members of the Joint Advisory Board were present during the event and took part in the morning panels.

The reimbursement term of reference was attached to the e-mail; the document outlined the reimbursement process and eligibility criteria for Advisory Board members participating in the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Conference.

4 BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Conference

4.1 Participation

Altogether, 81 people participated in the event, out of 93 registrations, indicating a strong turnout (87% attendance rate). Policymakers, Advisory Board members, schemes and label owners, industry actors, NGOs, academia, EU projects representatives related to bio-based systems were present (Figure 1).

Figure 1. BIOBASEDCERT Final Conference

An overview of participant statistics from the 13th of May is detailed in Table 4:

Table 4: the participation in the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Conference

	N° Participants	81 over 93 subscriptions
Project	HARMONITOR	12
	STAR4BBS	23
	SUSCERT4BIOBASED	14
	Others	32
Profile	Academia	29
	Industry	15
	Civil society, including NGOs	15
	Policymaker	9
	Other	13

The audience represented a well-balanced mix of stakeholders, including (Figure 2):

- **Academia:** 29 participants, indicating significant interest from the research community;
- **Industry:** 15 participants, reflecting the relevance of certification schemes to business and market actors;
- **Civil society and NGOs:** 15 participants, underlining the importance of sustainability and transparency in bio-based systems;
- **Policymakers:** 9 participants, including representatives from the European Commission, highlighting the strategic policy relevance of the event;
- **Other stakeholders:** 13 participants, including consultants, independent experts, and project partners.

Figure 2. Participation profile- BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Conference

In terms of project representation:

- STAR4BBS had the highest presence with 23 participants;
- HARMONITOR followed with 12;
- SUSCERT4BIOBASED contributed with 14 participants;
- **31 attendees** came from outside the cluster projects, demonstrating the event's strong outreach and broader relevance.

Overall, the first day was marked by **high participation, cross-sectoral representation, and active engagement**, setting a solid foundation for in-depth discussion and collaboration on the role of certification in sustainable bioeconomy.

4.1 Outputs

During the day key results from the BIOBASEDCERT cluster were shared, linking them to the broader European bioeconomy policy framework.

Discussions covered the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), assessment of certification schemes and labels, trade flow analysis, and cost-benefit evaluations. The focus was on exploring how voluntary sustainability certification systems can function as effective policy tools for a sustainable circular bioeconomy. A highlight of the event was a European Commission DG RTD.B1-led workshop on: "Bio-based products in the frame of the Ecodesign for sustainable products Regulation and the Consumer empowerment Directive".

Throughout the event, insights on how voluntary sustainability certification systems can serve as effective policy tools for a sustainable circular bioeconomy were explored. Key takeaways and policy recommendations were documented, with the day concluding in an integrative session to synthesize findings.

After the opening made by Luana Ladu, Astrid Ladefoged (Unit Green Transitions, DG Research & Innovation at European Commission) and Stefania Rocca (Project Officer, European Research Executive Agency, REA), the first session, named **“Exploring the applicability of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) as a co-regulation instrument”**, provided a short overview of the BMT, including its structure, core functionalities, and key findings from its two-phase testing process. The discussion focussed on the potential of the BMT to support EU policy objectives, particularly in fostering the uptake of sustainable bio-based materials. Special attention was given to the tool's use as a voluntary or co-regulatory instrument within current or forthcoming EU legislative frameworks on bio-based products. The panel explored the BMT's relevance to sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs), its potential alignment with regulatory instruments (such as RED III), and its long-term integration in the broader EU sustainability governance landscape.

The day continued with the **Workshop: “Bio-based products and certification in the frame of the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and the Consumer Empowerment Directive”**. The policy framework that designs and steers the pathway of the EU industry towards the green transition includes the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation and the Consumer Empowerment Directive. This workshop explored the progress of the bio-based industrial value chains along such a pathway, bringing together experts from the projects' consortia. Panellists examined how the Empowering Consumers Directive and the ESPR influence bio-based products (in scope of the legislation), particularly in areas such as sustainability claims, certification schemes, and labelling—including the introduction of Digital Product Passports (DPP). Additionally, discussions focused on the necessary developments, including research and innovation efforts, to align both traditional bio-based products—such as textiles, wood-based and bio-based construction materials, paper packaging, detergents, and lubricants—and innovative bio-based solutions with the requirements set by these regulations. The panel discussion was highly dynamic, highlighting both the challenges and opportunities in aligning bio-

based products with evolving EU regulatory requirements; key challenges included the complexity and cost of certification, fragmented policy implementation, and the need to enhance the credibility of sustainability claims. At the same time, opportunities emerged through the adoption of Digital Product Passports (DPP), the potential of co-regulatory tools like the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool, and the strategic use of voluntary certification schemes to improve transparency, facilitate market access, and support compliance with EU sustainability objectives.

Highlights from the first panel are reported in the Table 5 below:

Table 5: highlights from the 1st panel

<p>Experts Bio-lines</p>	<p>Lara Dammer, leads the Economy and Policy Department at the nova-Institute and chairs the policy working group of the Renewable Carbon Initiative. Her work focuses on the political framework for the use of renewable raw materials, carbon capture and use, recycling, environment, climate, agricultural and energy policy; as well as market analyses. Lara holds a master in Political Science, History and English Literature.</p> <p>Luca Boniolo is a Programme Manager at ECOS, the Environmental Coalition on Standards, focusing on sustainable and circular textiles. Luca advocates for legislation and standards aimed at making textile products more sustainable and circular and preventing waste and pollution. Luca holds a Master's in International affairs and political science.</p> <p>Maira Devisscher with ISEAL since 2015 managing ISEAL’s Innovations Fund. Since 2023, she has represented ISEAL in two Horizon projects focused on understanding the role of certification schemes and labels in the biobased sector. She has recently led the revision of the ISEAL guide for benchmarking sustainability systems. Maira holds an MA in Environment, Development and Policy, an MBA in Entrepreneurship, and a BA in International Relations.</p> <p>René Bethmann has nearly 20 years of experience in material and innovation management. Now Senior Innovation Manager at VAUDE, he drives cutting-edge projects in material innovation, with a strong focus on renewable carbon strategies. He is also an Advisory Board</p>
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	<p>Member of the Renewable Carbon Initiative (RCI). Rene holds a degree in Textile and Apparel Technology</p> <p>Ivana Krkljuš innovative sustainability strategist at BASF, specialized commercializing sustainable solutions. She holds a PhD from the Max Planck Institute for Intelligent Systems and Business Sustainability Management as well as International Relations and the Political Economy certifications from esteemed institutions, the University of Cambridge, and the London School of Economics and Political Science.</p> <p>Floris Akkerman is head of the section of Ecodesign and Energy labelling at BAM. During the last 15 years, he has advised the German government during negotiations for a number of EU regulations on minimum energy efficiency standards and energy labelling. Floris holds a PhD in Chemistry.</p>
<p>Question: Sustainable product design and production are key for a green economy, for example when setting product requirements under ESPR. What role can bio-based materials/products play in these terms? What are best-practice (and worse too) examples from the sector?</p>	
<p>Lara Dammer</p>	<p>The Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) introduces a set of horizontal sustainability criteria that apply across various product sectors and material groups, including bio-based products. These criteria emphasize aspects such as reparability, durability, recyclability, and overall circularity, aiming to reduce environmental impacts throughout a product's life cycle. While recycled content is already a key focus within the ESPR framework, there is growing recognition that renewable content—a defining feature of bio-based products—should also play a more prominent role. Bio-based products span a wide range of sectors and materials, and integrating renewable content into the ESPR criteria would better reflect their unique sustainability potential and support the EU's broader green transition goals.</p>

<p>Floris Akkerman</p>	<p>In the context of implementing the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), it is crucial to ensure that regulatory frameworks do not unintentionally create barriers to innovation or market entry—especially for emerging sectors like bio-based products. As highlighted by Floris, overregulation or the creation of too many distinct material classes can lead to complexity, fragmentation, and inefficiencies in compliance and enforcement. Instead, the focus should be on developing clear, harmonized criteria that are broad enough to accommodate a wide range of materials—including bio-based ones—without stifling innovation. This approach would support a level playing field while still promoting sustainability goals. It also encourages the development of flexible, performance-based standards rather than prescriptive rules that may not suit all product types or material innovations. Ultimately, the goal should be to enable the green transition, not hinder it, by ensuring that regulations are inclusive, adaptable, and innovation-friendly.</p>
<p>René Bethmann</p>	<p>From the end consumer’s perspective, it is essential that industry actors comply with the relevant regulations, such as the ESPR and the ECD. As René emphasized, compliance is not optional - it is a necessary step to ensure that products meet the expected standards of sustainability, transparency, and safety. René emphasized as well that the ESPR should remain open and adaptable.</p> <p>Emerging technologies should be considered and not categorically excluded – this is particularly pertinent in the context of mass balance approaches. A level playing field is essential. The textile industry has already established robust standards and certification systems to ensure credible chains of custody. Any new systems introduced should be aligned with these existing frameworks; failure to do so would result in implementation costs that are not economically viable. It is also important to recognize that current chain-of-custody verification mechanisms are resource-intensive and costly, yet they do not deliver measurable benefits to end consumers. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), in particular, face significant barriers in meeting these requirements. This</p>

	<p>should be taken into account in policy design, and supportive tools should be made available to ease the burden on such enterprises.</p> <p>While environmental claims by companies are frequently criticized as greenwashing, it is often more accurate to describe these as cases of <i>greenwashing</i>. In many instances, misleading claims are the result of knowledge gaps rather than deliberate intent to mislead.</p>
<p>Question: What challenges and opportunities do you see related to sustainability claims and labelling in bio-based sectors – and how could these be addressed by Directive Empowering consumers /ESPR?</p>	
<p>Luca Boniolo</p>	<p>The Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and the Empowering Consumers Directive (ECD) present both challenges and opportunities for sustainability claims and labelling in the bio-based sector. As Luca highlighted, the ESPR is a groundbreaking regulation—it introduces mandatory information requirements, unlike the more voluntary nature of the ECD and Green Claims Directive. This shift creates a structured framework that can significantly influence how bio-based products are perceived and positioned in the market. The ESPR pushes away from the market the worst-performing products, but at the same time, it tries to pull consumers towards better-performing products. We see 3 main opportunities for bio-based products: i) Improved Consumer Understanding: currently, many consumers struggle to understand what these claims actually mean—especially in the case of bio-based products, which are not inherently sustainable. Clear, standardized labelling can help consumers make more informed choices based on verified environmental benefits. ii) Raising product performance ambition: by setting minimum performance thresholds, the ESPR encourages manufacturers to improve the sustainability of their products. This creates a pull effect, guiding consumers toward better-performing, more sustainable options while simultaneously pushing lower-performing products out of the market. iii) by having mandatory information we will have to decide (policy makers) on the</p>

	<p>methodology that will be used to measure specific impacts of the products.</p>
<p>Maira Devisscher</p>	<p>Biobased products are not inherently more sustainable – it depends on how the biomass was produced, the manufacturing processes, the end-of-life characteristics, etc. Yet, we often see biobased products marketed as ‘ecological’, ‘environmentally friendly’, ‘sustainable’ or using some other generic sustainability claim. That will change with the Empowering Consumers Directive, which moves us away from generic statements and works to provide consumers (and companies) with clearer and more reliable information about the sustainability characteristics of a product. The Directive will also help to create a more fair playing field businesses that are committed to sustainability.</p> <p>The continued challenge with claims and labelling in bio-based products though is that their value chains are very complex, and there is a wide range of certification schemes and labels that play different functions in the chain. We want to empower consumers to make more informed choices but how do we achieve clear and accurate communication for consumers when there is so much to communicate? How do we avoid confusing and overwhelming consumers? I look forward to learning more about digital product passports and how it can help bridge that challenge.</p>
<p>Question: Digital Passport: What is the state-of-the art of digital passport (DPP) for bio-based products? How do you work-towards alignment with technical/infrastructure (DPP technical standards being developed) and with the potential data/information requirements for products under ESPR? What data or information would you recommend forming part of the DPP for bio-based products?</p>	
<p>Ivana Krkljus</p>	<p>The Digital Product Passport (DPP) is emerging as a cornerstone of the EU’s sustainability agenda under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR). If I were to summarize the aim of DPP in one sentence, it would be striving for increased traceability along the value</p>

	<p>chain. Practically, this means end-to-end product LCA (or cradle-to-cradle).</p> <p>The chemical industry produces 70,000 products for 15 industrial sectors. Furthermore, legislation regulates substances, not products. In complex formulations, there are often more than 60 substances, which means the chemical sector needs to provide transparency for 70,000 products multiplied by the number of substances.</p> <p>We are taking proactive steps to prepare reporting on predefined categories for priority product groups (textiles & apparel, furniture, tires, mattresses, and beyond), supporting customers in transition.</p> <p>Regarding the DPP for bio-based products, I refer the product parameters listed in the ESPR Annex I and the product aspects mentioned in Article 5, e.g., the use of sustainable raw materials, the environmental footprint of products, the carbon footprint of products, the use of substances of concern, and resource use and efficiency.</p>
<p>Floris Akkerman</p>	<p>The DPP is a key instrument under the ESPR aimed at enhancing transparency, market surveillance and traceability. As Floris emphasized, the DPP's strength lies not only in providing information to consumers and businesses but also in enabling market surveillance in sectors that are traditionally harder to monitor. The DPP serves three objectives: i) transparency, making product information accessible to all stakeholders including consumers; ii) market surveillance: supporting regulatory enforcement and compliance; iii) traceability; enabling tracking of materials and components throughout the value chain.</p> <p>Although apparel and textiles are currently prioritized in the ESPR work plan, the data requirements and methodologies being developed are highly relevant and transferable to bio-based products. These include: Material composition (e.g., fibre types in textiles or feedstock types in bio-based goods); Recycled content Substances of concern; Production processes and environmental impacts;</p>

<p>René Bethmann</p>	<p><u>Consumer Perspective on the Digital Product Passport (DPP):</u></p> <p>From a consumer standpoint, there appears to be limited support for the DPP. Its added value for end users remains unclear. Considering the EU energy Label, a consumer is making a decision based on cost-savings during the usage.</p> <p><u>Rationale for a Consumer-Facing DPP:</u></p> <p>The intended benefits include promoting more sustainable consumer behaviour – for example, by encouraging reduced washing frequency. However, it is important to question whether such behavioural shifts can be effectively driven through product-level data. Instead, regulatory attention may be more appropriately focused on addressing business models that incentivize overconsumption.</p> <p><u>Concerns Regarding the Current ESPR Approach:</u></p> <p>The current focus of the ESPR on product longevity and durability, particularly through specific testing parameters, may be premature. The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodology, which underpins much of the assessment framework, is not yet sufficiently developed to reliably support such durability testing.</p> <p><u>On Fast Fashion and Consumer Behaviour:</u></p> <p>It is critical to acknowledge that fast fashion is primarily driven by consumer demand patterns, not solely by corporate practices. Effective policy must therefore consider behavioural drivers and systemic consumption incentives alongside supply-side regulation.</p>
<p>Luca Boniolo</p>	<p>The objectives of the DPP can be found in the ESPR regulation and are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) ensure that actors along the value chain can easily access and understand product information relevant to them; (b) facilitate the verification of product compliance by competent national authorities; and

	<p>(c) improve the traceability of products along the value chain.</p> <p>The DPP should be an instrument used not only to convey information, but also to further increase the traceability in the value chain, in terms of both location and impacts of the various steps and tiers.</p>
<p>Question: The role of certification schemes of bio-based products in light of the Directive Empowering consumers and/or ESPR</p>	
<p>Maira Devisscher</p>	<p>Credible certification schemes have welcomed the ECD because it essentially legislates good practice - it's in line with the requirements that we have in the ISEAL Code regarding credible claims and with our guidance on effective claims management.</p> <p>Based on their standards, their assurance and traceability systems, certification schemes enable users to make different types of claims and they have robust claims policies to manage those claims. They can help the biobased sector meet the requirements of the ECD in two main ways: 1) through sustainability labels – the ECD explicitly prohibits the display of sustainability labels not based on a certification scheme (or established through public authorities), and 2) by providing reliable, clear and accurate information to substantiate specific environmental claims. This aspect of substantiation of environmental claims is picked up by the Green Claims Directive, which also recognises the value of voluntary environmental labelling schemes.</p> <p>ISEAL shares the objective that sustainability or green claims in the EU marketplace should be clear, relevant, and substantiated to enable consumers to make more informed and sustainable purchasing decisions. We believe that the community of voluntary sustainability standards has a lot of valuable experience that is useful for the design and implementation of green claims legislation. On our website we share the detailed analysis of the ECD and the Green Claims Directive that we submitted to EU institutions capturing the perspective of certification schemes.</p>

Question: Coming to R&I: what is necessary to do/develop in order to improve the environmental sustainability performances – both for traditional/commercial bio-based products and innovative bio-based products – also with the view of addressing the objectives of the Directive Empowering consumers and the ESPR?

Ivana
Krklijus

The concept of bioeconomy is gaining significant global traction, evolving from its early focus on resource substitution and biotechnological innovation to a more comprehensive and cross-cutting model for sustainable development. Bioeconomy is often facing critiques for perpetuating unsustainable land and biomass use. We need to imagine new pathways both within and beyond the window of political or social acceptability. Sustainable use of biomass use should be evaluated through a mix of indicators, primarily descriptive- and performance-type indicators providing insight on system aspects of state, pressure and impact.

On R&I here are points outlining what is required to support startups and bioeconomy development:

1. Access to Funding: Startups need financial support to cover initial costs and ongoing operations.
2. The raw material costs must be reduced: A growing number of non-EU countries, such as the U.S., China, and Brazil, are rapidly expanding their bioeconomy sectors by providing significant state subsidies, maintaining lower environmental standards, and imposing fewer regulatory barriers.
3. Shared Resources: Access to Scale-up infrastructure, shared facilities, and open-access test facilities, is crucial for startups. These facilities allow startups to conduct experiments and trials without the burden of significant capital investment, facilitating innovation and accelerating the development of new products. For example, shared pilot plants, funded to facilitate cost-effective fermentation for all companies, including larger ones, would be highly beneficial.
4. Training and Education: Industry knowledge, mentorship programs to effectively address challenges,

along with fostering public-private partnerships between industry and academia.

5. **Networking Opportunities:** Facilitating connections with industry professionals and potential partners is essential for growth.

6. **Market Access:** Providing pathways to market entry can help startups reach customers more effectively.

The discussion sparked strong interest among the public, leading to a thought-provoking question from the audience: "Why focus so much on the production phase and not on consumption? The consumption phase accounts for more than 50% of environmental impact, and if we used products more effectively, this would increase."

Several panellists addressed this important point:

- **Ivana Krkljus** acknowledged that the use (consumption) phase is often overlooked. However, she emphasized that significant benefits, particularly in terms of greenhouse gas (GHG) savings, can be observed during this phase.
- **Luca Boniolo** highlighted the need to balance efforts. To stay within planetary boundaries and promote circularity, it's essential to both enhance the sustainability performance of products and tackle the issue of overproduction. These approaches should not be seen as conflicting but rather as complementary. He also stressed the importance of avoiding consumer-blaming and instead holding companies accountable for their actions and omissions.
- **Floris Akkerman** pointed out the critical role of education. While regulation is necessary, it does not cover every aspect of the sustainability challenge. In many cases, well-informed consumers can drive change more effectively than regulation alone.

The following session, **Session II: "Impact of certification on global bio-based value chains"** explored the critical role of certification schemes in shaping global bio-based value chains, highlighting their influence on sustainability, market access, and regulatory compliance. Key insights from sister projects were presented, showcasing the main results achieved and the lessons learned. The session also addressed the

challenges, barriers, and opportunities faced by certification schemes across bio-based value chains. During the interactive segment participants shared their perspectives and collaboratively identify potential solutions to overcome existing barriers, fostering resilient and sustainable bio-based value chains.

Highlights from the panel is reported in the table below (Table 6):

Table 6: highlights from the 2nd panel

<p>Experts Bio-lines</p>	<p>Myrna van Leeuwen is a senior researcher specialising in the bioeconomy and environmental economics at Wageningen Economic Research. Her work focuses on the assessment of sustainable and circular agricultural systems, with a particular interest in the environmental impacts, economic feasibility, and policy dimensions of bio-based value chains. She is actively engaged in modelling and scenario analysis to support EU policymaking on land use, climate change mitigation, and food systems transformation. Her research spans topics such as circular economy, agricultural production, consumer behaviour, certification, and value creation, with regional expertise in Europe, including the EU, Netherlands, and Eastern Europe. She contributes to integrated frameworks that bridge science and policy, aiming to support the transition towards climate-neutral, resource-efficient, and resilient economies.</p> <p>Gabriela Lopez Camey is a sustainability and forestry specialist currently serving as Benchmarking Coordinator at Preferred by Nature, where she supports the development and evaluation of certification and sustainability frameworks across global value chains. With a strong background in tropical forestry and resource management, she holds an MSc in Tropical Forestry from Technische Universität Dresden and has gained international experience through roles in Germany, Guatemala, and Taiwan. Her work bridges environmental standards, forest governance, and sustainable land use, focusing on strengthening the credibility and impact of sustainability certification schemes. Gabriela brings deep expertise in benchmarking sustainability indicators and supporting multi-stakeholder processes to improve environmental and social outcomes in the bioeconomy.</p>
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Luciano Proto Cassina is a Scientist & Project Manager at nova-Institute, with dual MSc degrees in Bioeconomy and Agricultural Economics; he specialized in policy analysis, market analysis, and techno-economic evaluations supporting the transition to a circular bio-based economy .

At nova Institute, Luciano leads work on EU and World Bank-funded initiatives, focusing on bio-based products and materials, valuation methodologies, and policy frameworks. He also co-hosted a nova-Session in June 2024 on the latest EU policy framework for Renewable Carbon, where he guided discussions on the CSRD, ESRS, and CSDDD. Luciano's research bridges agriculture, bioeconomy, and policy, offering integrated market and regulatory insights.

General highlight of the session

Among the key contributions, the cluster presentation emphasized that the feasibility of certification schemes depends on achieving a careful balance between costs and benefits, as well as opportunities and challenges. Case studies analysed within the cluster demonstrated a net positive impact of certification, though the extent of the benefits varied significantly by actor type, feedstock, and regional context. Notably, the analysis was constrained by limited data availability, underscoring the need for more robust and standardized information. The discussion also highlighted that feasibility challenges extend beyond financial considerations to include operational, governance, and market-related barriers.

Based on these findings, a series of recommendations were proposed to enhance both the effectiveness and understanding of certification feasibility in the bioeconomy. These include improving knowledge on the costs and benefits of certification, promoting the standardization of data collection and harmonization of indicators, and encouraging consistent reporting on environmental, economic, and social externalities. Additionally, the cluster called for strengthening support infrastructure through financial incentives, targeted training, and improved

	<p>market access. Further research was recommended to identify entry points for change by addressing the barriers and challenges that hinder certification uptake.</p> <p>On the policy level, the speakers advocated for greater alignment of certification requirements across energy and material sectors as well as bio-based and fossil-based industries, to ensure a level playing field. National governments were urged to enhance the efficiency of policy implementation and monitoring, while also promoting inclusive multistakeholder dialogue and addressing power imbalances between stakeholders. Finally, the session underscored the importance of co-developing certification schemes with strong legal foundations that balance credibility and feasibility, always keeping the sustainability of the bioeconomy as the guiding principle.</p>
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Session III: “Assessing the feasibility of voluntary sustainability certification: costs, benefits, challenges and ways forward” addressed the overall feasibility of voluntary sustainability schemes, presenting key results from the cluster’s research on (economic) feasibility: key challenges of certification, important costs and benefits, as well as enabling factors to address challenges and knowledge gaps identified. Panellists, representing several stakeholders, addressed strategies to overcome challenges and increase feasibility.

Highlights from the panel are reported in the Table 7 below:

Table 7: highlights from the 3rd panel

<p>Experts Bio-lines</p>	<p>Costanza Rossi (SQ-Consult): she is working on the economic feasibility of sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels (CSLs) and doing a PhD at Utrecht University (The Netherlands).</p> <p>Lusine Aramyan (WR): a senior scientist at market and chains group at Wageningen Economic Research) holds an MSc in agricultural economics and a PhD in measuring performance in agri-food supply chains. Lusine has more than 10 years of relevant experience in food chain research projects and has an extensive publication list in</p>
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international peer-reviewed journals, mainly focused on agri-food supply chain management. Her research expertise is on economics of agri-food supply chains with the specific focus on chain performance, market intelligence, efficiency analyses including food waste reduction, and innovations.

Sofia Maria Ioannidou (AUA): she is a Chemical Engineer with an MSc in bioprocess engineering from the Department of Food Science and Human Nutrition at the Agricultural University of Athens. Her research are focused on sustainability assessment of bio-based systems and biorefinery development. More specifically, her studies cover techno-economic and environmental integrated sustainability assessment for the bio-based economy, sensitivity analysis and profitability risk assessment as well as Life Cycle Costing (LCC) for bio-based processes.

Yuki Hamilton Onda Kabe (Braskem): he is a Chemical Engineer by training and has 20 years of experience in sustainability and life cycle management. He has an extensive experience in corporate GHG accounting and CDM projects. He is active in the life cycle community serving as reviewer for several UNEP Life Cycle Initiative publications and in the board of directors of the Forum for Sustainability through Life Cycle Innovation (FSLCI).

Laura Väyrynen (ECOS): Sustainability professional with expertise in ESG data, corporate sustainability, and anti-greenwashing, currently serving as Programme Manager – Environmental Transparency at ECOS. With experience spanning consulting, ESG reporting, and sustainability strategy, she holds an M.Sc. in Sustainability Management (University of Toronto) and a B.Sc. in Business Administration (University of Turku). Her work is driven by a commitment to biodiversity, rewilding, and transforming economic systems for a more sustainable future.

Harmen Willemse (Better Biomass): he is a project manager with more than eleven years of experience in the field of standardisation and certification and extensive knowledge of stakeholder management. Working with a quick understanding of the technical details, while keeping the overall strategic perspective. He works at Better Biomass, the international sustainability certificate for all types of

	<p>biomass, including biofuels, solid and gaseous biomass as well as biobased products later on this year.</p> <p>Joyce de Wit (RVO): she is working at RVO, the Dutch regulator and policy advisory organisation in the fields of sustainability, agriculture, innovation and international business. Her work focuses on implementation of the RED criteria in national legislation, the use of certification in legal contexts for the use of sustainable biomass in biobased products and bioenergy, and the carbon transition from fossil to renewable in general.</p>
<p>Question 1: What do you expect/hope policymakers and regulatory bodies will do to improve feasibility of voluntary sustainability certification?</p>	
<p>Joyce de Wit (RVO)</p>	<p>To improve the feasibility of voluntary sustainability certification, policymakers and regulatory bodies are expected to integrate these schemes with incentives—for example, by making certification a condition for receiving subsidies. It is also important that new sectoral regulations begin with flexible, not overly detailed requirements, allowing them to evolve and become more stringent over time. Finally, harmonising legal frameworks across Europe, particularly in diverse areas such as maritime, aviation, and plastics, is crucial to ensure consistency and broader adoption.</p>
<p>Question 2: What action can different stakeholders (policy makers, businesses, certification owners, auditors, technology developers) take to increase the visibility of benefits of certification?</p>	
<p>Joyce de Wit (RVO)</p>	<p>To increase the visibility of certification benefits, all stakeholders must prioritise the credibility of private certification systems. Communicating the outcomes of certification supervision and audits can strengthen public trust and demonstrate reliability. The upcoming Green Claims Directive will also play a key role in reinforcing this credibility. Additionally, transparent reporting of scheme activities and measurable results is essential for making the</p>

	benefits of certification more visible and tangible to both the public and decision-makers.
Question 3: What measures can certification scheme owners take to ensure their standards are both rigorous and achievable for businesses of all sizes?	
Joyce de Wit (RVO)	To ensure their standards are both rigorous and achievable for businesses of all sizes, certification scheme owners should focus on cost efficiency and consider offering group certification to support small enterprises. Aligning with recognised frameworks such as ISO or ISEAL, and following guidance like that in the revised RED implementing regulation 996, can strengthen credibility. Moreover, providing clear, detailed guidelines for both users and auditors helps maintain audit quality and consistency while improving accessibility and understanding across different business scales.
General highlight of the session	
Joyce de Wit (RVO)	I think it is good to have regular interaction between scheme owners and policy makers who intend to use schemes in a legal context to make sure that certification can be used as efficient as possible. There will always be tension between the voluntary nature of certification and obligatory legal requirements and it is good to be aware of that before deciding on certification as a legal instrument. And to be aware of scheme management practises and timelines needed for new requirements to materialise in practise.

The final session, **Session IV: “How can voluntary sustainability certification schemes drive the transition to a sustainable bioeconomy”** was a dynamic and interactive session to summarize the most valuable insights derived from the work and discussion of the day and the meetings of the Roundtable of Certification Schemes promoted by the BIOBASEDCERT cluster, focussing on key strategic recommendations. Participants engaged in translating project results into actionable future

steps, identifying critical gaps, and providing inputs for shaping policies directions to drive the establishment of a sustainable circular bioeconomy.

A key element of the session was the presentation and discussion of the clusters' joint policy recommendations⁴. The discussion of the recommendations was supported by short Mentimeter sessions, allowing the participants to provide feedback on the previous contributions during the session. This discussion covered aspects such as:

- Ensuring the effective and meaningful implementation of the BMT;
- Establishing continuous dialogue and information sharing with policymakers on the complexity of CSLs and their integration into policy frameworks;
- Strengthening the credibility, robustness, and effectiveness of CSLs;
- Developing and improving databases for trade flow monitoring, supported by harmonized EU-wide standards for the collection and analysis of trade data.

Highlights from the panel are presented in the Table 8 below:

Table 8: highlights from the 4th panel

Experts Bio-lines	<p>Sergio Ugarte (SQ Consult): Sergio holds a PhD in Mechanical Engineering, with minors in Economics and Mathematics. Sergio's combined technical and political expertise has brought him to the management of various complex, international and multi-disciplinary projects related to energy and development issues for a large number of public and private clients across Europe and other continents.</p> <p>Stefan Majer (DBFZ): Dr. Stefan Majer leads the “Applied Sustainability Assessment” working group within the Bioenergy Systems Department at DBFZ, where he develops and standardises Life Cycle Assessment, Life Cycle Costing, and social LCA methodologies to evaluate biomass energy sustainability. His work includes creating decision-support</p>
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⁴ Please check **D7.7 Final clustering report for HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07** and **D7.9 Final Policy Brief** for further information; those will be available on the Zenodo Community as soon as approved by EC “

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tools addressing indirect land use change and greenhouse gas impacts, underpinning policy-relevant analysis in the bioenergy sector.

Susanna Albertini (FVA New Media Research) is an expert in multimedia communication and stakeholder engagement, specialising in bioeconomy, sustainable education, and co-creation processes. With a background in psychology and organisational communication, she also serves as a Horizon 2020 evaluator and teaches in the Sustainability Management executive Master SUSTMAG at Unitelma Sapienza

Iris Vural Gürsel – Wageningen Research is a Senior Scientist in Biobased Products within the Chain Design & System Analysis group at Wageningen Research. Holding a PhD (cum laude) in Chemical Engineering, she specializes in sustainability assessment of biomass-derived products—applying lifecycle and techno-economic analyses. Iris has coordinated multiple national and EU projects on biorefineries and biobased conversion technologies, delivering actionable insights to support policymakers and industry shift toward a circular bioeconomy

Birka Wicke (Radboud University) is a Professor of Land, Climate & Sustainability at Radboud University, specializing in sustainable pathways for agriculture and the bio-based economy, with emphasis on land-use impacts and climate change mitigation. Her interdisciplinary research draws on environmental and social sciences—including land change science, industrial ecology, economics, and political science—to develop integrated solutions. Wicke endeavours to inform policy and practice on land-use emissions, greenhouse gas responsibility, and sustainability trade-offs.

Piergiuseppe Morone (Unitelma Sapienza) is a Full Professor of Economic Policy and Director of the School for Sustainability and Circular Economy (SUSTAIN) at Unitelma Sapienza, University of Rome. He researches innovation economics, evolutionary economics, the circular bioeconomy, and sustainability transitions. He is Vice-Chair of the Scientific Committee of the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU) and serves as Editor-in-Chief of *Societal Impacts* (Elsevier)

General highlight of the session

Session IV provided key insights into the feasibility and transformative potential of voluntary sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs) within the bioeconomy. Drawing from research conducted by the BIOBASEDCERT cluster, the session underscored that feasibility hinges on achieving a balance between costs and benefits, as well as between emerging opportunities and persistent challenges. Case studies revealed that while SCSs offer net benefits, these vary significantly by actor, feedstock type, and regional context. Data limitations continue to constrain comprehensive assessments, and challenges extend beyond economic feasibility to include operational, governance, and market-related barriers.

To strengthen the role of certification in the bioeconomy transition, several strategic recommendations were discussed. These include the need for a more robust understanding of the costs and benefits of certification, harmonised data collection methods, and standardised indicators. Enhanced reporting on environmental, social, and economic externalities is critical to making certification outcomes more transparent and comparable. Supporting infrastructure—such as financial incentives, capacity building, and improved market access—is essential for uptake, particularly among small actors. The session also highlighted the need for harmonised policies across energy and materials sectors, bio- and fossil-based industries, and for more effective implementation and monitoring mechanisms at the Member State level.

A recurring theme was the importance of inclusive, multistakeholder dialogue that addresses resource and power imbalances across the value chain. Moving forward, certification schemes must strike a careful balance: maintaining high credibility and robustness while remaining feasible and inclusive. Ultimately, certification should be embedded within broader legislative frameworks and aligned with the overarching goal of fostering a truly sustainable bioeconomy.

5 Conclusions

The BIOBASEDCERT Final Conference successfully brought together a wide range of stakeholders to discuss the future of sustainability certification in the bio-based sector. With strong participation and active engagement across all sessions, the event provided a comprehensive platform to present the outcomes of the STAR4BBS, HARMONITOR, and SUSCERT4BIOBASED projects, and to position them within the evolving EU policy landscape.

Key discussions centred on the applicability and relevance of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), the alignment of certification systems with major EU legislative developments, and the feasibility of voluntary sustainability certification across global bio-based value chains.

The final session captured strategic insights and refined them into a set of possible policy recommendations aimed at enhancing the role of certification schemes in supporting a sustainable and circular bioeconomy. Stakeholder feedback, including inputs via an interactive Mentimeter session, emphasized the need for:

- Continued engagement with policymakers on the complexities and potential of certification schemes and labels (CSLs),
- Improved data systems for trade flow monitoring,
- Strengthened credibility and harmonization of certification practices.

Overall, the conference was an important milestone for the BIOBASEDCERT cluster, fostering cross-sectoral dialogue and laying the groundwork for further policy, research, and innovation efforts to advance sustainability in bio-based systems.

“ Sustainable bio-based systems via effective certification & labelling ”

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